

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

SEMEY TRAGEDY: DOCUMENTS AND NARRATIVE

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ABSTRACT

In this article severe consequences of one of the most tragic pages in the history of Soviet Kazakhstan are considered. In particular the Semipalatinsk nuclear test site is discussed on the basis of published collections of documents, visual content and narrative.

Keywords: atomic bomb, narrative, Kazakhstan, Semipalatinsk, nuclear test site.

Not so long ago, we celebrated the 30th anniversary of the closure of one of the world's largest nuclear test sites - the Semipalatinsk nuclear test site.

It is impossible to deny the role of the Semipalatinsk nuclear test site, which was established during the arms race between the USSR and the USA, in the development of Soviet science and averting the threat of a new world war.

However, it is also true that the existence of this historic base was accompanied by a huge, irreparable tragedy for the regions of our country.

For the Semipalatinsk nuclear test site, 18,500 km² of the territory of Kazakhstan has been allocated. This is almost equal in size to the territory of the State of Israel (20,770 km²). According to the OSCE, 456 nuclear explosions were carried out at the Semipalatinsk test site [1], 116 of which were carried out openly, i.e. in the airspace.

As we know, the power of the first explosion was 2,500 times greater than the power of the atomic bomb dropped on Hiroshima. Academician of the Academy of Sciences of the Kazakh SSR I. Ya. Chasnikov wrote that "1000 Hiroshimas were carried out at the Semipalatinsk nuclear test site" in his book "Echo of Nuclear Explosions" [2.93].

Atomic bomb testing, which lasted for 42 years, spread to the atmosphere, lithosphere, and hydrosphere. Thus, it poisoned the flora and fauna of the eastern region of the country, and the human body, causing suffering to hundreds of thousands of residents for years.

The horrifying consequences of the nuclear test site for the daily life of the region are evidenced by archival documents published by employees of the Presidential Archive and the Semipalatinsk Regional Archive of the Republic of Kazakhstan, such as "History of the Semipalatinsk Test Site 1951-1992." and "Kazakhstan for a nuclear-free world" (2011), published during the years of independence.

Archival documents testify that back in 1956-1958, scientific expeditions and doctors working in these regions openly declared the danger of testing for the population and proposed to stop ground testing of nuclear weapons.

Expeditionary research works at that time were conducted in several settlements of Abai, Makanshy, Urzhar districts of the Semipalatinsk region. They

checked food, grass, soil and human bodies. As a result, it was found that the amount of radiation in food products, including flour, wheat, rice, buckwheat, exceeds the norm by 8-44 times. In addition, they observed changes in the human body and discovered previously unknown types of diseases [3. 10-14].

The first data on the impact of tests at the Semipalatinsk nuclear test site became known as a result of medical and environmental studies conducted by the Academy of Sciences of the Kazakh SSR. The research was led by the Professor Bakhia Atshabarov. The work of the scientist based on the results of the research from those years, published in the years of independence, is a valuable source on this issue.

From the documents contained in these collections of documents, it is not difficult to see the moral and psychological consequences of the explosions for the local residents. The people were horrified. For example, there is a memo of the head of the State Security Committee (KGB) for the Semipalatinsk region. The author of the document cites excerpts from letters written by residents of the city of Semey and the Semipalatinsk region to their relatives living in other republics of the Soviet Union. The content of some of them is as follows:

The author of an unknown letter writes to an acquaintance in Tomsk that "... especially in the last 15 days, the number of emigrants from here has been increasing. Now they warn of an explosion in advance. We went out into the field at 12:00, it's dangerous to stay at home... Everyone is in a hurry to get out here," or V-y, a resident of Semipalatinsk, writes to his father in Starodub: "Dad, it's good that you left. Testing continues here. Our air is very polluted and radiation has increased."

The author of the third letter is a resident of Semey V.A. Ts-iy writes to his brother, who lives in Sudak, Crimean region: "I will leave Semipalatinsk as soon as I retire. I don't want to be an animal that is experimented on..." The owner of another letter, K-ya, a resident of Semipalatinsk, has wrote to her relative living in the Rivne region: "We want to leave this place for Ukraine. Life here is becoming more and more difficult. The air is very polluted, especially during the winter months... Houses are shaking from earthquakes, we need to leave this place as soon as possible... ».

This letter written to Novosibirsk belongs to a resident of Semipalatinsk: "There was an explosion at 11:00 on February 13. The house looked like it was going to collapse. The explosive power was 6 points. This happens to us often. Everyone began to suffer from white blood disease...". Another letter was sent by G. Ya, a resident of Semipalatinsk. He has wrote to Vladivostok "... Our Semipalatinsk is contaminated with radiation, we are like guinea pigs. Many people suffer from white blood disease, most of their internal organs are affected by cancer..."etc. [3. 41-46]

The local residents experiencing anxiety and fear were in a hurry to leave as soon as possible.

The number of sicknesses in the territories of Semipalatinsk, Karaganda and Pavlodar regions caused by the radiation was constantly growing. These include lung and breast cancer, lymphohemoblastosis, and other malignant pathologies. Overall, cancer has tripled since testing began. In areas close to the Semipalatinsk test site, many children were born with various devia-

tions in maturity, congenital diseases and malformations. According to experts, all this is due to genetic mutations caused by short-term and residual radiation.

All this also affected the human psyche, and increased the facts of suicides in the region.

Academician I. Y. Chasnikov wrote: "It is not surprising that in the region in 1959-1987 the level of leukemia tripled, the death rate increased sharply, and the birth rate of mentally retarded children increased several times. The number of birth of children with disabilities and suicides have increased significantly. Only in the village of Sarzhal, more than 40 cases of suicide have been registered in recent years, and this did not happen until 1964," [2.90]. We can clearly see this with visual content, as shown below.

It is not difficult to understand the kind of suffering, moral and psychological consequences the residents of those regions experienced as a result of genetic mutations that led to children being born with disabilities, with deformed limbs and monstrous malformations [4]:

Dead children of the Semipalatinsk nuclear test site

<https://yvision.kz/post/527260>

Families, women living in the region, were scared of conception and childbirth.

Kairbek Kuikov is a victim of those testings, but his desire to live and his creativity are exemplary. The

fear and anxiety of the people can be seen in the drawings of this artist, he has come to life without two arms [5]. This is undoubtedly the sentiments of the entire region.

Artist Karipbek Kuyukov

Despite the subjectivity of the recollections and interviews of the residents of the nuclear test site areas, and of the witnesses and victims, the documentaries in which those are expressed, are also a valuable source on this issue [6].

There are many documentaries about the Semipalatinsk nuclear test site, including the following documentaries by the American and British directors. The suffering of the region's families and inhabitants, and

the fear of giving birth and conception are confirmed in these films:

- After the apocalypse. Film, Documentaries ... Antony Butts

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RRXm1evB2Rg>

- **THE POLYGON** Documentary: Radioactive Kazakhstan Uncovered with Kimberley Hawryluk + Scott Chrisman

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hqCT27S74r0>

• **SEMIPALATINSK TEST SITE** - history of nuclear tests. Part 1 Creation of nuclear weapons Mikhail Shemelin

• **SEMIPALATINSK TEST SITE** - history of nuclear tests. Part 2 Nuclear confrontation Mikhail Shemelin <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-cuYs5jxHbE>

Films made by American and British directors

The increase in the number of incurable diseases, respective reduction in life expectancy, fear of conception and childbirth followed by reduction in the birth rate, an increase in suicides, all these could not but negatively affect the demographic situation in this region.

According to a special state commission data, established in 1992, 1.5 million people were harmed by this test site.

The closure of the Semipalatinsk nuclear test site is a historic event that coincided with the independence of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Kazakhstan went down in the world history as the first country to give up nuclear weapons.

The President of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev delivering a speech at the General Debate of the 77th session of the UN General Assembly expressed concern about the growing rivalry and negative rhetoric between the nuclear powers, as well as about the lack of progress in the framework of the NPT Review Conferences: "The world of today appears to have entered a new, increasingly bitter, period of geopolitical confrontation. The long-standing international system - based on order and responsibility is giving way to a new, more chaotic and unpredictable one. The global system of checks and balances has failed to maintain peace and stability.

The security architecture is eroding. Mutual distrust between global powers is dangerously deepening. The world is falling prey to a new set of military conflicts" [7].

Today, due to the aggravation of geopolitical conflicts in the modern world, the authorities of Kazakhstan have proposed that all the countries, including nuclear powers, to develop a plan to completely abandon nuclear weapons by 2045. [8].

References

1. <https://www.un.org/.../obse.../end-nuclear-tests-day/history>
2. Chasnikov, I. Ya. Echo of nuclear explosions / I. Ya. Chasnikov. - 2nd ed., ball. - Almaty: TOO "Print-S", 1998. - 172 pp.
3. From the history of the Semipalatinsk test site 1951-1992. Collection of documents. Editor-in-chief V. N. Shepel. - Almaty: APRK 2007. 128 pp. + 10. pp. incl.
4. Dead children of the Semipalatinsk nuclear test site <https://yvision.kz/post/527260>
5. K. Kuyukov. I was gripped by life-art // Ege-men Qazaqstan. August 28, 2020, page 3.
6. Sarseke M. The Tragedy Of Semei. - A documentary historical story. - Astana: Foliant, 2019. - 688 pp. (In Kazakh); Zhotabaev N. R. Long echo of nuclear tests. Almaty, 2011, 248 pp. (In Russian); Boztayev K. Semipalatinsk test site... Almaty, 1992, 296 pp. (In Russian)
7. Speech by the President of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev at the General Debate of the 77th session of the UN General Assembly <https://www.akorda.kz/en/speech-by-the-president-of-kazakhstan-kassym-jomart-tokayev-at-the-general-debate-of-the-77th-session-of-the-un-general-assembly-2082327>
8. The Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons – a new reality in the process of nuclear disarmament. Liter.kz. 18.06.2022, 16:46 <https://liter.kz/dogovor-o-zapreshchenii-iadernogo-oruzhiia-novaia-realnost-v-protssesse-iadernogo-razoruzheniia-mukhtar-tleuberdi-1655549729/>